

VINPOCETINE ATTENUATES EXPERIMENTAL HEPATIC CIRRHOSIS THROUGH MODULATING INFLAMMATORY AND FIBROGENIC SIGNALING PATHWAYS

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Article Received on 15 May 2026,
Article Revised on 05 June 2026,
Article Published on 10 June 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20643146>

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How To Cite This Article: Mona E. Mogahed*, Rania R. Abdelaziz, Hoda E. Kafil. (2026). Vinpocetine Attenuates Experimental Hepatic Cirrhosis Through Modulating Inflammatory and Fibrogenic Signaling Pathways. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(6), 1933-1943. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Background: Liver cirrhosis has become a global issue that could threaten people all over the world. Different etiologies and chemicals can induce liver cirrhosis, such as Thioacetamide (TAA). Vinpocetine (Vinp) is considered a cerebrovascular drug because it has both anti-inflammatory and antifibrotic properties. The present study aims to explore the relieving impact of Vinpo against TAA-induced liver cirrhosis in Wistar rats. **Methods:** Male Wistar rats were treated with Vinpo at two different doses (10 and 20 mg/kg) orally, concurrently with TAA injection (200 mg/kg i.p twice weekly) for 12 weeks. Liver enzymes were measured in serum, while histopathological staining with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) was done in hepatic tissue homogenate. **Results:** Vinpo significantly reduced liver enzymes in serum (GPT and GOT), aligning with the regression of interlobular fibrous connective tissue proliferation compared to the TAA group. **Conclusion:**

Vinpo could be used as an innovative therapeutic agent against TAA-induced liver cirrhosis via its antifibrotic, antiproliferative properties.

KEYWORDS: Vinpocetine– Thioacetamide – Liver Cirrhosis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Chronic liver diseases (CLDs) are a public health challenge worldwide. CLDs are the 12th leading cause of death globally. In 2021, chronic liver diseases caused 1.43 million deaths (**Zhang et al., 2026**). Cirrhosis is an advanced level of CLD. It is a consequence of chronic liver damage and inflammation, characterized by diffuse hepatic fibrosis, with normal liver structures replaced by regenerative liver nodules. Cirrhosis can be caused by a variety of conditions, such as alcohol consumption, nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), hepatitis viruses, and autoimmune diseases. Cirrhosis may worsen to hepatocarcinoma and lead to death (**Liu & Chen, 2022**).

The liver is a chief organ in the body, as it is a major site for drug metabolism. The liver releases a variety of enzymes that convert endogenous or exogenous lipophilic chemicals into more polar metabolites (**Patel, Rahimi & Cassagnol, 2026**). Byproducts of this chemical processing may include reactive chemical intermediates that can attack hepatocytes, leading to hepatotoxicity (**Gu & Manautou, 2012**).

Many chemicals and techniques can induce liver injury in rats, simulating that in humans, but Thioacetamide (TAA) is a reproducible model and gives sufficient time for study (**Ezhilarasan, 2023**). Thioacetamide (TAA), with molecular formula C_2H_5NS , is an organosulfur compound. TAA is a well-established agent for inducing cirrhosis (**Kaur et al., 2017**). It is metabolized via Cytochrome P450 family 2 into free radical derivatives. Thereby, TAA was used to induce liver cirrhosis in the present study (**Sepehrinezhad et al., 2021**).

Several studies have demonstrated the protective effect of antioxidants on the liver against TAA-induced cirrhosis. Silymarin (SIL) is a standard treatment for managing conditions such as chronic liver disease. SIL is an effective hepatoprotective drug (**Vargas-Mendoza et al., 2014**). It was also reported to be safe and well-tolerated clinically. It protects liver cells by several mechanisms. It has antioxidant properties, anti-inflammatory properties, and antifibrotic effects. Thereby, SIL was used as a reference drug in the present study. (**Balkrishna et al., 2026**).

Vinpocetine (Vinpoc), methyl ester derivative of vincamine alkaloid, is an inhibitor of phosphodiesterase type-1 (PDE1). It is widely used in the management of cerebrovascular disorders, as it enhances cerebral blood flow. Additionally, it is a potent anti-inflammatory

and antioxidant in alleviating ischemia-induced damage in the peripheral organs, the kidney, and the liver. Hence, it is supposed that Vinpo has the ability to improve liver cirrhosis status (Azouz *et al.*, 2022; Vizi & Kiss, 2026).

The effects of Vinpocetine on liver cirrhosis were assessed in tissue and serum samples, and the underlying mechanisms were elucidated.

1. MATERIALS AND METHODS

1.1. Materials

- Vinpocetine (Vinpo) was purchased from the pharmacy as an active constituent of Vinporal® tablets (5 mg).
- Silymarin (SIL) was purchased from the pharmacy as an active constituent of legalon® capsules (140 mg).
- Thioacetamide (TAA) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich Chemical Co (St. Louis, MO, USA).

1.2. Preparation of drugs

- Vinporal® tablets were broken into tiny crystals and suspended in 0.5% carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) (El-Baz *et al.*, 2024) for oral administration.
- The powder of the legalon® capsules was dissolved in normal saline for oral administration.
- TAA crystals dissolved in normal saline for intraperitoneal injection.

1.3. Animals

Wistar rats, aged 8 weeks, were obtained from Vacsera, Giza, Egypt. They weighed 200 ± 30 grams in the beginning of the study. Rats were allowed free access to food and water and were kept in wire-bottomed stainless-steel cages. They were maintained in a temperature-controlled room (25 ± 3 °C) and kept on a 12h/12h light/ dark cycle. The experimental protocol was approved by the Mansoura University Animal Care and Use Committee (MU-ACUC) (Approval Code: PHARM. MS. 22.09.1), which strictly complies with the NIH guidelines.

1.4. Experimental protocol

The rats will be randomly assigned into 6 groups (8 rats/group) as follows:

- **Control group:** Rats received standard laboratory chow.

- **TAA group:** Rats received 200 mg TAA/kg body weight intraperitoneally twice a week for 12 weeks (Aydin *et al.*, 2010).
- **SIL50 + TAA group:** Rats received 200 mg TAA /kg body weight intraperitoneally twice a week concurrently with silymarin 50 mg/kg body weight orally once daily for 12 weeks (Okiljević *et al.*, 2024).
- **SIL100 + TAA group:** Rats received 200 mg TAA /kg body weight intraperitoneally twice a week concurrently with silymarin 100 mg/kg body weight orally once daily for 12 weeks (Kim *et al.*, 2016).
- **Vinpo10 + TAA group:** Rats received 200 mg TAA /kg body weight intraperitoneally twice a week concurrently with Vinpocetine 10 mg/kg body weight orally once daily for 12 weeks (Zaki & Abdelsalam, 2013).
- **Vinpo20 + TAA group:** Rats received 200 mg TAA /kg body weight intraperitoneally twice a week concurrently with Vinpocetine 20 mg/kg body weight orally once daily for 12 weeks (Zhu *et al.*, 2024).

1.5. Isolation of specimens

After 12 weeks, rats were anesthetized with secobarbital (50 mg/kg, i.p.). Blood samples were obtained from the retro-orbital venous plexus and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4 °C to collect serum, which was kept at -80 °C till subsequent analysis. Then, the liver was harvested, dried, and weighed. The left hepatic lobe was extracted, and a portion was homogenized in phosphate-buffered saline (10 % w/v) and centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4 °C to separate the supernatant, which was kept at -80 °C for further analysis. The right hepatic lobe was fixed in neutral buffered formalin (10 % v/v) for histopathological examination.

1.6. Assessment of liver function biomarkers

Levels of glutamic-pyruvate transaminase (GPT, Cat. No: 11409006, AGAPPE kit, India) and glutamic oxaloacetic transaminase (GOT, Cat. No: MBS2019147 My biosource Co., San Diego, CA 92195-3308, USA) as hepatic indices for liver function status were determined in serum according to the instructions provided by the manufacturer.

1.7. Histopathological analysis

To assess histopathological lesions, Liver tissue (i.e. 1 cm × 1 cm × 0.5 cm) was taken from the largest right lobe of the liver and fixed in 10% of formalin solution for 1 week. The liver tissue was dehydrated using a sequence of ethanol solutions, embedded in paraffin, and sectioned into 5 µm in thickness at 50 mm intervals followed by staining with hematoxylin-eosin (HE) dye (Suriawinata, Antonio & Thung, 2009).

1.8. Statistical analysis

Data were statistically evaluated using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's Kramer multiple comparisons test for parametric measures. Data are presented as mean ± standard error, and significance was accepted at $p < 0.05$. Analysis and figures were performed using Graphpad software Prism 8.4.2.

2. RESULTS

2.1. Effects of Vinpocetine on the liver function biomarkers

As illustrated in Fig. 1, serum glutamic-pyruvate transaminase (GPT) [A] and glutamic oxaloacetic transaminase (GOT) [B] activities were markedly elevated in the TAA-treated group, showing 3.6-fold and 2.3-fold increases, respectively, compared to the control group. While treatment with SIL50 or 100 mg/kg, Vinpo 10 or 20 mg/kg significantly ($p < 0.05$) attenuated these elevations. GPT activity was reduced by 28%, 59%, 15% and 39%, while GOT activity decreased by 17.5%, 56.6%, 22.9%, and 56.6% respectively, relative to the TAA group.

Fig. 1: Impact of SIL (50 and 100 mg/kg), Vinpo (10 and 20 mg/kg) on Liver function biomarkers: [A] glutamic-pyruvate transaminase (GPT) and [B] glutamic oxaloacetic

transaminase (GOT) in TAA-induced liver cirrhosis in rats. Data are expressed as mean \pm SE (n = 8/group). *, #, ^, @, and & significant differences (p< 0.05) versus the control, TAA, SIL (50mg/kg), SIL (100mg/kg) and Vinpo (10 mg/kg) groups, respectively, as determined by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey–Kramer multiple comparison test.

2.2. Effects of Vinpocetine on the histological changes

- Control group: Liver from the control group showing normal hepatic parenchyma; note the normal polyhedral hepatocytes (h), normal blood sinusoids (arrow), and normal central vein (C), (H&E X400), (Lesion Score: 0)
- TAA group: Microscope images of (H&E)-stained liver sections of the TAA group showing disarrangement of the hepatic cords, central veins, and portal areas, fibrous expansion of portal areas with infiltration of leukocytic cells (thin arrows), and marked portal bridging, as well as portal-to-central bridging leading to pseudo-nodules formation (Lesion Score: ++++). Low magnification X: 100 bar 100 and high magnification X: 400 bar 50.
- SIL (50 mg/kg) + TAA group: Liver sections from this group showing mild regression of the interlobular fibrous connective tissue proliferation (arrow), together with moderate degenerative changes inside the hepatic lobules (*), (H&E X200), (Lesion Score: ++)

- SIL (100 mg/kg) + TAA: Liver sections from this group showing mild regression of the interlobular fibrous connective tissue proliferation (arrows), and intralobular regeneration of normal hepatocytes (h), (H&E X200), (Lesion Score: +)
- Vinpo (10 mg/kg) + TAA: Liver sections from this group showing mild regression of the interlobular fibrous connective tissue proliferation (arrow), together with mild degenerative changes inside the hepatic lobules (*), (H&E X400), (Lesion Score: +)
- Vinpo (20 mg/kg) + TAA group: Liver sections from this group showing marked regression of the interlobular fibrous connective tissue proliferation (arrow), and intralobular regeneration of normal hepatocytes (*), (H&E X400), (Lesion Score: 0)

3. DISCUSSION

Liver cirrhosis is a significant global health challenge. Over 185 million individuals are infected globally in 2025 (Faruk *et al.*, 2026). It starts with injury, worsens to fibrosis, which is characterized by activation of hepatic stellate cells (HSCs), Activated HSCs develop into myofibroblasts, which are responsible for the deposition of collagen fibers leading to liver cirrhosis (Zhang *et al.*, 2016).

Compared with the other chemically induced cirrhosis models, the TAA-induced cirrhosis model is preferred because of its reproducibility, low mortality, and reduced toxicity. To induce liver cirrhosis, rats were administered TAA (200 mg/kg i.p., twice weekly for 12 weeks). TAA is metabolized via cytochrome P450 2E1 into free radicals called thioacetamide sulfoxide and thioacetamide-S (S-dioxide), which are hepatotoxicants (Bieche *et al.*, 2007). The produced free radicals prevent RNA from moving from the nucleus to the cytoplasm, causing liver damage and elevating serum liver biomarkers.

In the present study, TAA group showed the highest levels of serum ALT and AST compared with other groups. In contrast, vinpocetine and silymarin groups showed decreased levels compared with the TAA group. These results matched those from another study, where Vinpo could markedly attenuate liver injury by reducing GPT and GOT levels (El-Baz *et al.*, 2024). Several studies have reported higher serum levels of AST and ALT in rats that developed cirrhosis by TAA (Chandrashekar *et al.*, 2023). Thereby, the marked improvement in biochemical parameters is evidence that Vinpo can alleviate liver injury.

Moreover, TAA could induce histopathological changes which include disarrangement of the hepatic cords, central veins, and portal areas, fibrous expansion of portal areas with infiltration of leukocytic cells, and marked portal bridging, as well as portal-to-central bridging leading to pseudo-nodules formation. Our findings matched with the results of previous studies (**Dwivedi, Jena & Kumar, 2020; Darweish et al., 2021**), which used TAA in a 200 mg dose for the induction of fibrosis for 6 days and TAA at 100 mg for 18 weeks for the induction of cirrhosis in rats, respectively.

On the other hand, the control group showed normal liver tissue, intact hepatic lobules, and healthy portal areas and interlobular stroma. Likewise, SIL and Vinpo showed marked dose-related regression of fibrous tissue proliferation with newly formed bile ductulus, together with intralobular regeneration of normal hepatocytes in a trial for alleviation of portal cirrhosis compared to the TAA group. These findings are consistent with the results of earlier research on a model investigating the protective effect of Vinpocetine on liver fibrosis in the bile-duct ligated rat (**Hassan, Abouelfadl & Abdel-Salam, 2020**). In that research, oral treatment of Vinpocetine was able to decrease liver damage and fibrosis, as well as maintain the liver architecture.

Hepatic cirrhosis treatment focuses on attenuation of inflammation, inhibition of stellate cell activation, and suppression of extracellular matrix production. In the present study, silymarin was employed as a reference control because of its well-documented antifibrotic and anti-inflammatory properties. Using serum analysis for liver biomarkers and histopathological examination, the effects of vinpocetine on liver cirrhosis were determined. In conclusion, vinpocetine produced therapeutic effects comparable to those of silymarin, suggesting its potential as a promising agent for the management of liver cirrhosis.

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